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Coccidiosis of domestic food animals in Africa: a systematic review and meta-analysis

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ABSTRACT: A systematic review and meta-analysis of studies on coccidiosis in domestic food animals in Africa spanning the period from 2002 to 2022 was done with the objective of identifying the distribution of studies on the infection and aggregation of prevalence of the parasite in the study animals. A total of 43 articles met the eligibility criteria for inclusion in the review. These include 16 studies on cattle, 9 on sheep, 7 on goats, 2 on pigs and 18 on poultry. The results revealed pooled data from 8,717 cattle, out of which 3,211, representing 36.84%, were positive for coccidiosis. In sheep, a total of 1,916 samples were pooled, out of which 895 representing 46.71%, were positive for the disease. In goats, 2,148 samples were pooled, out of which 1,316, representing 61.26%, were positive for the disease. Two studies gave a total of 610 samples in pigs, out of which 78, representing 12.78%, were positive for coccidiosis. In poultry, 7,261 samples were pooled, out of which 2,894, representing 39.86%, were positive for coccidiosis. There were however, no significant differences in prevalence between the five species. The concentration method of ova and parasite examination was the commonest method of isolation of *Eimeria* identified in the current review. In conclusion, *Eimeria* infection is high in food animals in Africa. Therefore, to tackle the disease, there is a need for a concerted effort in the identification, diagnosis and general prevention and control of the disease.

Keywords: Prevalence; *Coccidia* infection; *Eimeria* infection; Fecal floatation; Meta-analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

Animal protein is a major component of human food requirements. It is obtained from the raising of food animals domestically and/or from hunted animal species in the wild. However, a major threat to the continuous supply of animal protein, is disease. Diseases have the potential to reduce the productivity of animals or even cause their death. This may, therefore, result in a decrease in available animal protein.

One major disease that transcends many species of both domestic and wild animals, and poses a significant threat to sustainable animal protein supplies is coccidiosis. Coccidiosis is a protozoal disease of animals affecting both domestic and wild species. The disease is caused by the intracellular protozoa, *Coccidia*, belonging to the phylum Apicomplexa [1]. The parasite is further classified into class Sporozoa, Subclass Coccidiasina, Order Eucoccidiorida, and Suborder Eimeriorina as cited by Lindsay et al. [2].

Eimeria species cause varying degrees of infections in many animal species, including cattle, sheep, goats, buffaloes, rabbits, and poultry worldwide, as cited by Gupta et al. [3]. *Eimeria* infections are often characterized by severe enteric complications in affected animals, resulting in severe economic losses [4]. With their special affinity for the cells of the gastrointestinal tract, coccidia causes considerable morbidity and mortality in affected animals. Some species of *Eimeria* are non-pathogenic, or even if they cause infection, they may not be lethal, however, the risk of these species becoming opportunistic or highly pathogenic is very possible.

Coccidia infections are prominent in young animals, with adult animals showing mild or no clinical signs. In dairy animals, for instance, coccidiosis is prevalent in young animals with heavy mortality, whereas adult animals show a sub-clinical form of the disease and act as a source of infection to newly added stock and young animals [3]. Over the years, a wide range of treatments have been used to control infections from these parasites, however, the potency of these treatments continues to dwindle. There is also the possibility of the mildly pathogenic species evolving into opportunistic more virulent pathogens.

This study, therefore, aimed at evaluating data on *Eimeria* infections in food animals in Africa, identifying the distribution and the trend of the disease, and also taking stock of the prevalent species associated with the disease across the region.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A systematic search of literature and publications on the coccidiosis of domestic animals in Africa from 2002 to 2022 was done in Google Scholar and PubMed using the following terms: coccidia infections of domestic animals, coccidiosis of animals in Africa, *Eimeria* infection in domestic animals, and Eimeriosis of food animals. The last search was done on the 10th of November 2022. A search in the Cochrane database of systematic reviews revealed no existing registration for related reviews.

2.1. Eligibility criteria

Eligible articles were selected based on the following criteria: studies on coccidian or *Eimeria* infections conducted in Africa and published or translated into English. Studies that did not calculate or provide data that can be used to calculate the prevalence of *Eimeria* infection among designated animal populations were excluded. Figure 1 gives a summary of the criteria for the selection of articles in the current study.

Figure 1. Flow chart of literature search and selection.

2.2. Data compilation

Data compiled for the study were; study location, sample size, species of domestic animals studied, type of samples collected, how samples were processed, prevalence of identified coccidia species, and overall prevalence.

2.3. Data analysis

The data was stored in Microsoft Excel and exported into Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 26 for analysis. The analysis was grouped into frequency, distribution, proportions/percentages, prevalence and risk ratio, as well as analysis of variance among data from the various species.

3.0 RESULTS

3.1. Distribution of studies and prevalence of *Eimeria* infection

A total of 98 articles were identified from Google Scholar and PubMed. However, 43 articles met the inclusion criteria for the current study. These include 16 studies on cattle, nine on sheep, seven on goats, two on swine, and 18 on poultry. Of the 16 studies on cattle, 11 were conducted in Ethiopia, 3 in Nigeria and 1 each in Kenya and South Africa. For the sheep, 5 studies were conducted in Ethiopia, and 2 each from Nigeria and Egypt. Out of the 7 studies on goats, 3 were done in Nigeria, and 2 each in Ethiopia and Egypt. One study each on pigs was conducted in Nigeria and Ethiopia. Of the 18 studies on poultry, 8 were conducted in Ethiopia, 4 in Nigeria and 1 each in Algeria, Kenya, South Africa, Somalia, Tunisia and Libya.

Of a pooled data of 8,717, cattle, 3,211, representing 36.84%, were positive for *Eimeria* infection. In sheep, a total of 1,916 samples were pooled from the 9 studies, out of which 895, representing 46.71%, were positive for *Eimeria* infection. In goats, 2,148 samples were pulled from 7 studies, out of which 1,316, representing 61.26%, were positive for *Eimeria* infection. Two studies gave a total sample size of 610 pigs, out of which 78 representing 12.78% were positive for *Eimeria* infection. In poultry, a total of 7,261 samples were pooled from 18 studies, out of which 2,894, representing 39.86%, were positive for *Eimeria* infection. Overall, 20,652 animals across five species were screened for *Eimeria* infections, out of which 8,394 were positive for various species of *Eimeria* giving a prevalence of 40.6% (Table 1, Table 2).

Table 1. Statistics of samples from five animal species for the isolation of *Eimeria*.

Animal species	Number of studies	Number of samples obtained	Number of negative samples	Number of samples positive	Prevalence (%)	Risk Ratio (+ cases/-cases)
Cattle	16	8,717	5,506	3,211	36.84	0.58318
Sheep	9	1,916	1,021	895	46.71	0.876592
Goats	7	2,148	832	1,316	61.26	1.581731
Pigs	2	610	532	78	12.78	0.146617
Poultry	18	7,261	4,367	2,894	39.86	0.662697
Total	54	20,652	12,258	8,394	40.64	0.684777

The study shows a risk ratio of exposed animals getting *Eimeria* infection to range from 0.14 in pigs - to 1.58 in cattle, with an average of 0.68 across the five animal species (Figure 2). The present review identified a total of 45 *Eimeria* species isolated from five species of animals in 21 different studies. These include 14 species in cattle, 13 in sheep, 10 in goats and 8 in poultry.

Table 2. Analysis of variance of prevalence among five species.

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Total number of samples	Between Groups	732714.616	4	183178.654	2.049	.103
	Within Groups	4201268.461	47	89388.691		
	Total	4933983.077	51			
Number of positive samples	Between Groups	94161.340	4	23540.335	.909	.466
	Within Groups	1217099.660	47	25895.737		
	Total	1311261.000	51			

Figure 2. Risk ratios among the various species.

The only two studies on pigs however, did not specify the species of *Eimeria* isolated from those studies. Tables 3 and 4 shows the distribution of studies and *Eimeria* species isolated from the five animal species covered in the current study. From the current review, the concentration method of ova and parasite examination involving either flotation or sedimentation techniques were the most used, with two studies using the microscopic examination of mucosal scraping. The floatation technique either used the Sheather’s solution, saturated salt or sugar solution.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 Study distribution and prevalence

The current review does not only aggregate the prevalence of *Eimeria* infections in some domestic animals across Africa, but also gives a distribution of studies and the prevalence of the parasites in specific locations within the region. From the current review, the highest number of studies on *Eimeria* infections in Africa were done in poultry in the last 20 years. This suggests the importance of the disease to the poultry industry, causing significant losses to farmers and the economy as a whole. According to Teng et al. [4], *Eimeria* infection affects the intestine of chickens, by impairing the epithelial cells, leading to a fall in nutrient digestibility and poor growth performance. Commercial poultry production is a highly capital-intensive venture, and very vulnerable to the least disturbance, compared to livestock, hence the increased stakeholder attention to the sector. Studies in pigs were the least frequent with an average of 1 in 10 years, suggesting the lesser severity of the disease in the species. From the data, it is obvious that not much work has been done on *Eimeria* infections in animals in the African region.

Table 3. Statistics of studies on *Eimeria* infection in some domestic animals.

Author(s)	Year	Country	Species	No. of samples	No. of positives	Prevalence (%)	Method	<i>Eimeria</i> species isolated
[19]	2022	Ethiopia	Sheep	422	132		Flotation technique	
[20]	2022	Ethiopia	Cattle	265	119	45.0	Flotation, Sheather's sugar solution	<i>E. bovis</i> , <i>E. zuerni</i> , <i>E. alabamensis</i> , <i>E. ellipsoidalis</i> , <i>E. subspherical</i> , <i>E. auburnensis</i> , <i>E. wyomingensis</i>
			Sheep	119	69	58.0		<i>E. ovinoidalis</i> , <i>E. ahasta</i> , <i>E. parva</i> , <i>E. crandallis</i> , <i>E. granulosa</i> , <i>E. hawkinsi</i> , <i>E. intricata</i> , <i>E. pallida</i>
[21]	2020	Nigeria	Cattle	478	186		Flotation technique	<i>E. bovis</i> , <i>E. zuernii</i> , <i>E. auburnensis</i> , <i>E. cylindrica</i> , <i>E. subspherica</i> , <i>E. canadensis</i> , <i>E. bukidnonensis</i> , <i>E. alabamensis</i>
[22]	2020	Egypt	Sheep	184	126	68.4	Flotation technique	<i>E. ahsata</i> , <i>E. bakuensis</i> , <i>E. crandallis</i> , <i>E. webybridgensis</i> , <i>E. faurei</i> , <i>E. granulosa</i> , <i>E. ovinoidalis</i> , <i>E. intricate</i> , <i>E. marsica</i> , <i>E. pallida</i> , <i>E. parva</i>
[9]	2020	Ethiopia	Sheep	197	172	87.31	Flotation (Sheather's solution)	<i>E. crandallis</i> , <i>E. ovinidallis</i>
			Goat	187	159	85.03	Flotation (Sheather's solution)	<i>E. arloingi</i> , <i>E. ninakohlyakimovae</i> , <i>E. christenseni</i>
[23]	2019	Egypt	Goat	225	173	76.89	Flotation and sedimentation	
[8]	2018	Ethiopia	Cattle	232	169	72.7	Flotation (saturated NaCl)	-
[6]	2018	Egypt	Sheep	142	82	57.7	Flotation technique, (Saturated saline)	<i>E. crandallis</i> , <i>E. granulosa</i> , <i>E. ovina</i> , <i>E. parva</i> , <i>E. faurei</i> , <i>E. ovinoidalis</i> , <i>E. intricata</i> , <i>E. pallida</i> , <i>E. arloingi</i> , and <i>E. ahasta</i>
			Goats	135	81	60.0		<i>E. nina kohlyakimovae</i> , <i>E. hirci</i> , <i>E. caprina</i> , <i>E. christenseni</i> , <i>E. jolchijevi</i> , <i>E. apsheronica</i> , <i>E. arloingi</i>
[24]	2018	Ethiopia	calves	384	206	53.6	Flotation (saturated salt solution of NaCl)	-
[25]	2018	Nigeria	Cattle	295	4	1.36	Flotation and sedimentation techniques	-
			Goat	147	2	1.36		-
			Sheep	120	15	12.5		-
			Cattle	556	74	13.3		-
[26]	2017	Nigeria	Goat	212	31	19.3	Direct Fecal Smear Method	-
			Sheep	86	36	65.1		-
			Pigs	226	32	18.6		-
[27]	2017	Kenya	Cattle	983	322	32.8	Flotation (MacMaster technique)	-

Author(s)	Year	Country	Species	No. of samples	No. of positives	Prevalence (%)	Method	<i>Eimeria</i> species isolated
[28]	2017	Ethiopia	Calves	384	186	48.4	-	-
[29]	2017	Ethiopia	Calves	384	81	21.1	Flotation technique	-
[30]	2017	Ethiopia	Calves	384	122	31.8	Flotation technique	<i>E. bovis</i> , <i>E. zuernii</i> , <i>E. auburnensis</i> , <i>E. Canadensis</i> , <i>E. ellipsoidalis</i> , <i>E. cylindrical</i>
[7]	2016	Ethiopia	Calves	384	240	62.5	Flotation technique	-
[31]	2016	Ethiopia	Sheep	384	88	22.9	Flotation technique	-
[14]	2016	Ethiopia	Cattle	384	73	19.01	Flotation technique.	-
[32]	2016	Ethiopia	Calves	900	218	24.2	Flotation technique	-
[33]	2016	Ethiopia	Calves	384	278	72.4	Flotation technique	<i>E. bovis</i> , <i>E. zuernii</i> , <i>E. auburnensis</i> , <i>E. canadensis</i> , <i>E. ellipsoidalis</i> , <i>E. subspherica</i> , <i>E. cylindrical</i> , <i>E. alabamensis</i> , <i>E. wyomingensis</i> , <i>E. bukidnonensis</i>
[34]	2015	Ethiopia	Pigs	384	46	12.0	Flotation technique and histopathological examination	-
[35]	2012	Ethiopia	Cattle	384	87	22.7	Flotation technique	-
[36]	2009	Nigeria	Goat	1120	816	72.8	Flotation	-
[37]	2009	Ethiopia	Sheep	262	175	66.8	Flotation using Sheather's sugar solution	<i>E. parva</i> , <i>E. crandallis</i> , <i>E. pallida</i>
			Goat	122	54	44.3		<i>E. arloingi</i> , <i>E. ninakohlyakimovae</i> , <i>E. faurei</i>
[38]	2002	South Africa	Calves	958	670	70.0	Flotation (Modified McMaster technique)	<i>E. zuernii</i> , <i>E. bovis</i> , <i>E. ellipsoidalis</i> , <i>E. pellita</i> , <i>E. alabamensis</i> , <i>E. subspherical</i> , <i>E. brasiliensis</i> , <i>E. auburnensis</i> , <i>E. canadensis</i> , <i>E. bukidnonensis</i> , <i>E. cylindrica</i> , <i>E. illinoisensis</i>
			Adult cattle	978	176	18.0		

Table 4. Statistics of studies on *Eimeria* infection in poultry.

Author	Year	Country	Species	No of samples	No of positives	Prevalence (%)	Method of examination	<i>Eimeria</i> species identified
[39]	2022	Somalia	Poultry	384	76	19.8	Flotation technique	-
[40]	2021	Libya	Pigeon	100	72	72.0	Flotation technique	<i>E. labbeana</i>
[41]	2019	Ethiopia	Poultry	384	162	42.2	Flotation technique	-
[42]	2018	Algeria	Poultry	256	171	66.8	Flotation technique	<i>E. acervulina, E. tenella, E. maxima, E. brunetti, E. mitis</i>
[43]	2018	Ethiopia	poultry	224	48	21.4	Flotation technique	-
[44]	2017	Ethiopia	Poultry	384	250	65.10	Flotation (McMaster Technique)	-
[45]	2017	Nigeria	Poultry	200	84	42.0	Sedimentation method	<i>E. acervulina, E. tenella, and E. maxima</i>
[46]	2016	Nigeria	Poultry	384	154	40.1	Flotation technique (saturated salt solution)	<i>E. necatrix, E. maxima, E. tenella, E. mitis, E. acervulina, E. praecox, E. brunetti</i>
[47]	2016	Nigeria	Poultry	600	191	31.8	Flotation technique, (McMaster counting tech.)	-
[48]	2016	Tunisia	Poultry	630	200	31.8	Microscopic examination of mucosal scraping and fecal flotation (saturated solution of sugar)	<i>E. tenella, E. maxima and E. acervulina</i>
[49]	2015	Ethiopia	Poultry	384	278	72.4	Flotation technique	-
[50]	2015	Ethiopia	Poultry	394	222	56.3	Flotation and microscopic examination of mucosal scraping	-
[51]	2015	Ethiopia	Poultry	384	75	19.5	Flotation technique	<i>E. acervulina, E. tenella, E. maxima, E. necatrix, E. burneti, E. mitis</i>
[52]	2013	Ethiopia	Poultry	767	427	55.7	Flotation technique	<i>E. acervulina, E. brunette, E. maxima, E. mitis, E. necatrix E. praecox, E. tenella</i>
[53]	2012	Ethiopia	Poultry	638	142	22.3	Microscopic examination of mucosal scraping	<i>E. tenella, E. brunette, E. necatrix, E. acervulina, E. maxima</i>
[54]	2010	Kenya	Poultry	710	192	27.04	Flotation (McMaster counting technique)	-
[55]	2010	Nigeria	Poultry	261	93	35.5	Flotation technique (saturated NaCl)	-
[56]	2003	South Africa	Poultry	177	57	32.0	Flotation (McMaster and Visser sieve techniques)	-

Prevalence may be defined as the sum of existing cases of a disease in a population at a particular time [5]. In the present review, the aggregated prevalence of *Eimeria* infection in the five animal species ranged from 12.78% to 61.26%, with an average prevalence of 40.6%. According to Mohamaden et al. [6], *Eimeria* infection in sheep and goats is largely subclinical. Therefore, despite the highest prevalence of *Eimeria* in goats and sheep (61.26% and 46.71%, respectively), as shown in the current study, the two species are not severely impacted by those infections. The high prevalence of infections in goats may also be attributed to the high-risk ratio of the disease among the species, as shown in Figure 2. The prevalence of the disease in poultry is the third highest, closely followed by cattle. A high prevalence of a disease is a product of its high incidence and long duration (course) of the disease. The high figures of prevalence recorded are thus an indication of the chronic nature of *Eimeria* infections if not treated. There were, however, no significant differences between the various species in terms of the prevalence of the disease, as shown in Table 2.

Clinical manifestations of *Eimeria* infection are the result of the interaction of multiple factors such as species, age of animal, management and husbandry practices, number of oocysts ingested, hygienic conditions, season, and temperature, among others as cited by Asfaw et al. [7]. However, age, among other risk factors, has the most influence on the susceptibility of animals to *Eimeria* infections [8]. The high prevalence of the parasite in animals, as shown in the current study, therefore suggests poor animal management systems and husbandry practices by farmers and caregivers. According to Mohamaden et al. [6], *Eimeria* infections in most species are sub-clinical. However, some important biochemical changes in the serum samples of affected animals have been identified. This means that, even in cases that are less severe, with animals showing mild or no clinical signs, there could be an accumulated effect on the overall well-being of the animals. There is also the potential for these parasites to develop into harmful opportunistic parasites that may end up causing severe infections in these animals. The highest risk ratio of exposed animals to being infected was 1.58 in cattle, whereas the lowest was 0.14 in goats. This suggests that exposed cattle stand the highest risk of being infected compared to the other species.

4.2. *Eimeria* species identified

In the current review, 14 species of *Eimeria* were identified in cattle, 13 in sheep, 10 in goats, and 9 in poultry. According to Etsay et al. [9], there are a dozen species of coccidia found in small ruminants; of these, a few are potentially highly pathogenic, whereas several others have little pathogenic effect under normal circumstances. This explains why most *Eimeria* infections are not severe. Small ruminants of all ages and breeds are susceptible to *Eimeria* infection, however, young animals from 3 weeks to 5 months of age are most severely affected by outbreaks of coccidia infection, while the rest of the flock might act as carriers, as cited by Mohamaden et al. [6].

While the current review identified 13 and 10 species of *Eimeria*, respectively in sheep and goats, Andrews [10], reported that, there are 11 recognized species of coccidia affecting sheep and nine in goats. Bawn and Htun [11], on the other hand explained that, 16 *Eimeria* species are identified in goats worldwide, with the species, *E. arloingi*, *E. ninakohlyakimovae*, *E. christenseni*, and *E. caprina* being the most pathogenic. The current review however, identified *E. ovinoidalis* and *E. crandallis* as the most commonly occurring species of the parasite in sheep. This is supported by the findings of Nourullahi-Fard et al. [12], who identified *E. crandallis* as the most prevalent species in sheep.

In goats, the current review identified *E. arloingi* and *E. ninakohlyakimovae* as the most commonly occurring species. This also, supports the findings of Bawn and Htun [11] as well as Kusiluka et al. [13] which

identified the two species as the most occurring in dry tropical areas.

About 13 species of *Eimeria* are noted to be responsible for infections in cattle, with the most pathogenic species being *E. bovis* and *E. zuernii* as cited by Yamral et al. [14]. However, in the current review, 14 species of parasites were identified, with 5 species, namely; *E. bovis*, *E. alabamensis*, *E. subspherical*, and *E. ellipsoidalis*, being the most prevalent in cattle. Susceptibility of cattle to *Eimeria* infections, and for that reason, prevalence was higher in young animals than in older animals.

In the current review, the highest number of studies among the five animal species was recorded in poultry. This could be the result of the negative impact of *Eimeria* infections on the industry, thereby attracting more attention. This is affirmed by Appiah [15], who avers that coccidiosis was the highest cause of mortality among chicks between weeks one and four. Also, Ayim-Akonor et al. [16] explained that, coccidiosis is one of the three most common diseases reported by farmers. The current review also identified *E. acervuline*, *E. tenella*, and *E. maxima* as the most prevalent species in *Eimeria* infections in poultry. This also corroborates the finding of Lopez-Osorio et al. [17]

4.3. Methods of isolation and identification of *Eimeria* species

Studies covered by the current review used flotation and sedimentation techniques, and in a few instances, microscopic examination of mucosal scraping, as the methods for the isolation of *Eimeria* species. A commonly used test for the diagnosis of *Eimeria* species in parasitological tests, is the ova and parasite examination [18]. This can be classified as; direct wet mounting, concentration, or permanent stain-smear [18]. However, the methods identified in the current review, namely faecal flotation and sedimentation techniques, are the two types under the concentration method.

5. CONCLUSION

Eimeria infections remain an important component of diseases affecting food animals in Africa. The disease is significantly present in Africa, and its prevalence in five animal species ranges from 12.76% in pigs to 61.26% in goats, with an overall average of 40.6%. However, there is no significant differences of prevalence between the five species. While the parasite appears not to be severely virulent, there is a risk of it becoming opportunistic and causing devastating outbreaks. To tackle the disease, there is a need for a concerted effort in the identification, diagnosis, and general prevention and control of the disease.

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